

Assessing OpenStreetMap bicycle data quality with BikeDNA: A Denmark Case Study

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Getting more people to commute by bike is increasingly accepted as a central element of making the transport system more sustainable. However, a modal shift towards more cycling requires vastly better bicycling conditions. At the moment, ambitious plans for bicycle infrastructure investments are being set up by numerous cities across the world (e.g., in Paris, Milan, Auckland, Bogotá). This uptick in investments is matched by a promising growth in data-driven cycling research. Due to its global coverage, OpenStreetMap (OSM) data play a central role in this context, both for research projects on bicycle infrastructure and for cyclist routing applications.

The quality of volunteered geographic information (VGI) and OSM data is well-studied, and most OSM data are shown to be of high quality. However, we know that errors and lower data quality are not randomly distributed in OSM, but instead correlate with lower population densities and vary both from country to country and within cities [1-4]. When it comes to bicycle infrastructure, lanes and dedicated cycling paths often are among the latter features to be mapped [5,6]. Moreover, the topological quality relevant for bicycling routing lags behind the quality of other road network data [5,6]. Even though these tendencies have profound implications for cycling research using OSM data, to date only few studies looked specifically at the quality of bicycle infrastructure data in OSM. Previous research on the quality of bicycle infrastructure data have shown that data quality issues are prominent in both administrative, commercial, and crowdsourced data sets, and that OSM data often are of a comparable or higher quality [3,4]. OSM data can therefore be an attractive data source – not just for researchers, but also for bicycle planners. Providing tools for reproducible quality assessment can help build the necessary trust in OSM data among people and agencies new to OSM data.

To address the current knowledge gap about bicycle infrastructure data in OSM, and to help others gain insights into the quality of OSM data in their local area, we have developed the tool [BikeDNA](#) [7]. BikeDNA is developed for reproducible and rigorous quality assessments of bicycle infrastructure and network data from OSM or elsewhere, based on a

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series of easy to use Python Jupyter notebooks. BikeDNA is particularly useful for studying the entirety of the bicycle network at a city/regional scale. BikeDNA builds on existing methods for spatial data quality assessment, but is tailored specifically to the peculiarities of bicycle infrastructure data, such as a high network fragmentation and inconsistent data models within and between different data sets.

The tool incorporates both intrinsic and extrinsic methods, i.e., both a standalone evaluation of OSM data properties and a comparison with another reference dataset. BikeDNA accounts for different data availability scenarios and is applicable even if no reference dataset is available. Moreover, for the extrinsic part of the analysis, our approach does not assume that the reference dataset is of higher quality, but is rather focused on identifying where OSM and the reference data differ. BikeDNA can thus be used for extrinsic data quality assessment even when there is no high-quality data on cycling infrastructure available.

The methodology is oriented towards data usages for analyses of e.g. accessibility, routing, and other network-based approaches, and therefore supplements evaluation of data completeness with analysis of topology errors and variations in connectivity, and overall network structure. Data completeness is evaluated based on differences in infrastructure density between OSM and reference data, taking into account differences in data models and how the use of a center line mapping can undercount the amount of infrastructure compared to a data set mapping the exact location of bicycle tracks and lanes. Completeness is furthermore evaluated with a matching of corresponding features in OSM and reference data [8,9]. Data topology and network structure is assessed through an identification of, for example, over and undershoots and the location and size distribution of disconnected components. Finally, we evaluate the local completeness of OSM tags relevant to cycling. BikeDNA is based on existing libraries for working with spatial networks such as OSMnx, pyosm, NetworkX, and Momepy [10-13]. The tool is free to use and open-sourced under the AGPL-license.

Although OSM data quality is generally high, it is important to keep in mind how quality might deviate not just in some areas, but also for specific subsets of the data. Likewise, despite the frequent use of OSM data, localized data evaluation and assurance is still necessary to support e.g. public administrators and planners to adopt OSM in their work. Through this study and by providing BikeDNA as an open-source tool, we aim to make it easier for the cycling research and planning community to quickly assess the fitness for use of OSM data in their area, and to support and motivate the use of open and crowdsourced geospatial data when working with cycling and other modes of active mobility.

We demonstrate the use case of BikeDNA through a case study of the bicycle infrastructure data in Denmark from respectively OSM and a local administrative data set (Figure 1a and 1b). Through the case study we show how BikeDNA for example can identify differences in data completeness (Figure 1c); detect topological errors and unwanted network fragmentation (Figure 1d and 1e), and help users choose the data set most suitable for bicycle routing and accessibility analysis (Figure 1f).

Figure 1. Example outputs from running BikeDNA for a demonstration area in Greater Copenhagen with data on dedicated bicycle infrastructure from OSM and a local reference data set (GeoDanmark):
 Input data from a) OSM and b) GeoDanmark. c) Outcome of feature matching: Matched (blue) and unmatched (red). d) Examples of identified undershoots. e) Disconnected components in OSM data f) Largest connected components.

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